

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

ICOSLG functions in melanoma resistance.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Citations

1. Roussel, L., Landekic, M., Golizeh, M., Gavino, C., Zhong, M.C., Chen, J., Faubert, D., Blanchet-Cohen, A., Dansereau, L., Parent, M.A. and Marin, S., 2018. Loss of human ICOSL results in combined immunodeficiency. *Journal of Experimental Medicine*, 215(12), pp.3151-3164.
2. Hedl, M., Lahiri, A., Ning, K., Cho, J.H. and Abraham, C., 2014. Pattern recognition receptor signaling in human dendritic cells is enhanced by ICOS ligand and modulated by the Crohn's disease ICOSLG risk allele. *Immunity*, 40(5), pp.734-746.